

Toll-like Receptors In Periodontics - A Review

Srishti Shankar¹, Neelesh Singh², Abhilasha Mukherjee³

Received on: 17 August 2024; Accepted on: 06 September 2024; Published on : 20 October 2024

Assistant Professor¹
Department of Periodontology
Babu Banarasi Das College of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow

Associate Professor²
Department of Periodontology
Babu Banarasi Das College of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow

Assistant Professor³
T.S. Misra Medical College &
Hospital
Lucknow

Corresponding author

Dr. Srishti Shankar

Assistant Professor
Department of Periodontology
Babu Banarasi Das College of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow

Access this article online

Website : www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code

Abstract

The periodontium is a host to millions of microorganisms in health and disease. The first line of host defense mechanism is innate immunity, which is an inherited resistance to infection. The key factor for its function is toll-like receptors (TLRs). TLRs present on gingival epithelial cells, are under constant stimulation and hence produce cytokines and defensins, which maintains oral health. Against pathogens, it functions by recognising the pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMP). If this leads to a breach in the epithelial barrier, it results in an exaggerated release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, causing host tissue destruction. Hence, the current review highlights the dual edged sword nature of TLRs in periodontal health and disease.

Keywords : Periodontitis, TLRs, PAMPs, PRRs, immunity

Introduction

The first line of defense is the innate immunity, which shows an incredible differentiation between host and pathogens through a refined system based on toll-like receptors (TLRs).^[1] They are encoded by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), which are able to detect and differentiate between microbes of related groups through the pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). When the TLRs interact with PAMPs, innate immunity is activated via intracellular signaling pathways. Periodontitis is an inflammatory disease and research states that TLRs play an essential role in its resolution and exacerbation.

History

- Christiane Nüsslein-Volhard in 1985 identified a Toll gene in *Drosophila*, after which the TLRs are named, as they share a similar protein code.
- Jules A. Hoffman in 1996, that Toll gene is effective in providing immunity to *Drosophila* against fungal infection by the activation of antimicrobial peptides.^[2]
- Nomura et al in 1994 reported the first human TLR.
- Taguchi et al in 1996 mapped the human TLR to a chromosome.
- In 1997 it was observed that when TLR, artificially ligated with various antibodies, initiates the adaptive immune response.
- The fact that TLRs activate the innate

immune response was discovered by the mouse TLR4, which acts as a receptor for bacterial lipopolysaccharide

- Up until now 10 human TLRs have been recognized and they detect a varied number of PAMPs and signal the presence of infection.

Structure of the Human TLR

- A human TLR consists of^[3] [Fig 1]:
- N-terminal leucine rich repeat (LRR) domain - Common feature of PRRs which binds with ligand and is associated with signaling
- Cysteine rich region
- Transmembrane domain
- C-terminal cytoplasmic Toll/IL-1R (TIR) domain - important for activation of innate immunity

Fig. 1 - Structure of Human TLR

How to cite this article: Shankar et al. - Toll-like Receptors In Periodontics - A Review.
HTAJOCD 2024

TLR and their ligands

Cells of the innate immunity offering first line of defense express TLRs in response to specific microbial structures. [Fig. 2]

Toll-like receptor	Ligands
TLR 1	Triacyl Lipopeptides
TLR 2	Lipoproteins, Peptidoglycan, Lipoteichoic acid, Zymosan, <i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i> lipopolysaccharide & fimbriae, <i>Capnocytophaga ochracea</i> lipopolysaccharide
TLR 3	Double stranded RNA, Polyinosine-polycytidylic acid
TLR 4	<i>Escherichia coli</i> lipopolysaccharide, <i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i> lipopolysaccharide, <i>Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans</i> lipopolysaccharide, <i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i> lipopolysaccharide
TLR 5	Flagellin
TLR 6	Peptidoglycan, Lipoteichoic acid, Diacyl lipopeptides, Zymosan
TLR 7	Imidazoquinoline
TLR 8	Single stranded RNA, Imidazoquinoline
TLR 9	Bacterial DNA, CpG oligodeoxynucleotide
TLR 10	Not determined

Fig. 2 - TLRs & their Ligands

Expression of TLR in immune cells

Cells of innate immune system express the following TLRs^[4] [Fig 3]:

Cells	Toll like receptors
Neutrophils	TLR 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10
Monocytes/macrophages	TLR 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8
Myeloid dendritic cells	TLR 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10
Plasmacytoid dendritic cells	TLR 1, 6, 7, 9
B lymphocytes	TLR 1, 3, 6, 7, 9, 10
T lymphocytes (Th1/Th2)	TLR 2, 3, 5, 9
T lymphocytes (regulatory)	TLR 2, 5, 8

Fig. 3- TLRs Expressed by Immune Cells

- The first cells to reach the site of infection, recognize and respond to pathogens via TLRs, are the PMNs
- Macrophages, also forming the first line of defense, utilize TLRs to recognize, engulf and kill the microbes.
- Dendritic cells activate the adaptive immune response, through their 2 subtypes - Myeloid and Plasmacytoid cells

The TLR superfamily

TLR + IL-1 receptors form the receptor superfamily, called the "Interleukin-1 receptor/Toll-like receptor Superfamily"^[5]. All the members of this family have a TIR domain in their structure. 3 subgroups of this domain are :

- Produced by cells of the innate immune system and have extracellular immunoglobulin domain are in the proteins subgroup I TIR domain.
- Classical TLRs which bind directly or indirectly to PAMPs fall in proteins of subgroup II TIR domain.
- Exclusively systemic and mediate signaling from proteins of subgroup I and II, are in subgroup III TIR domain. (Dunne A et al, 2003)

TLR signaling

TLR signaling takes place through the Myeloid differentiation primary response protein - 88 (MyD88) dependent and

independent pathways^[6].

I. (MyD88) - dependent pathway :

- Essential for most TLR mediated cell activation
- In this pathway TLR activation is mediated by Myd88 molecule alone or in combination with TIR domain containing adaptor protein (TIRAP), which activates IL-1 receptor-associated kinase 4 (IRAK-4).
- IRAK-4 then unites with TNF receptor-associated factor 6 (TRAF6), thereby activating 2 distinct signaling pathways.
- 1. One pathway activates activator protein 1 (AP-1) through Mitogen activated protein kinase (MAK).
- 2. The other activates transforming growth factor- β -activated kinase 1 (TAK1). This leads to degradation of inhibitors of NF- κ B and its release, which translocates to the nucleus.^[7]

The end products of both these pathways lead to the release of cytokines and chemokines.

II. (MyD88) - independent pathway - through this pathway TLR 3 and 4 are activated^[8]

Specificity of innate immunity

The innate immune system has been recognized as an extremely specific system post the discovery of TLRs^[9]. The presence of PRRs which recognize and respond to distinct microbial structures, has resulted in this specific nature of innate immunity cells.

Also, the immune cells produce different cytokines in different quantities and of various quality, on stimulation by Gram + and Gram - bacteria, hence, highlighting the specificity of the response^[10].

The microorganism has the tendency to mutate, in order to escape recognition by the host, hence becoming a complicating factor. This challenge is met by innate immunity through the presence of PAMPs on pathogens and not on the host. This leads to a large number of pathogens being recognized by a limited number of immunity cells.

TLR in periodontal tissue and its role in health and disease

Immune cells are present in very low numbers, when observed histologically, in a healthy periodontium. Various cells of the periodontium express TLRs [Fig.4]. As the gingiva is constantly exposed to numerous PAMPs, the TLRs may play a significant role in maintaining periodontal health, by recognizing and responding to the PAMPs^[11].

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease and dental biofilm has been considered as a primary etiological factor. There is a shift in periodontal ecology as conditions change from health to gingivitis and finally progresses to periodontitis. There is a gradual increase in gram negative anaerobes and most importantly the presence of key periodontal pathogens *P.gingivalis*, *A.a* and *T.forsythia* in deep periodontal pockets. Hence the chronic stimulation of TLRs against the microorganisms may lead to exorbitant production of cytokines and chemokines, thereby causing tissue destruction^[12].

Periodontal Cells	Toll-like receptors	Function
Gingival epithelial cells	TLR 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 9	Increased attachment and migration of leucocytes towards antigen on lumen of the pocket, also induces production of Interleukin-8 (IL-8) as well as Matrix metalloproteinases.
Gingival fibroblasts	TLR 2, 4, 9	Increased production of Interleukin-8 as well as other pro-inflammatory cytokines.
Endothelium	TLR 1, 3, 4, 5	Production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, migration of immune cells towards gingival sulcus.
Osteoblasts	TLR 1, 4, 5, 6, 9	Upregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-8, Tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and biologic mediators responsible for bone resorption. Increased expression of receptor activator of nuclear factor κ B ligand (RANKL).
Osteoclasts	TLR 2, 4	Enhanced survival of osteoclasts and increased osteoclastic activities.
Cementoblasts	TLR 2, 4	Down regulation of RANKL.
Periodontal ligament fibroblasts	TLR 2, 4	Enhanced production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, release of proteases causing direct destruction of surrounding tissues.

Fig.4 - TLRs Expressed by Cells of Periodontium

TLR mediated progression of periodontal disease

1. Epithelial cells^[13]

- Primary cells to migrate towards gingival sulcus in response to PAMPs
- IL-8 is also released by these cells which leads to a surge in migration of neutrophils, leading to release of IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α in large quantities, causing tissue destruction.
- Also produce MMPs, which directly harm the periodontium.
- Through TLR-4, IL-8 stimulates endothelial cells, causing increased adhesion of monocytes.

2. Monocytes and Dendritic cells^[14]

- Release proinflammatory cytokines on being exposed to PAMPs
- On direct stimulation by bacterial LPS, may differentiate into osteoclasts.
- Maturation of dendritic cells takes place on being exposed to PAMPs. Hence they act as antigen presenting cells as well as lead to activation of Th1 or Th2 immune response, by the release of cytokines by T-lymphocytes^[15].

3. Gingival fibroblasts

- Stimulation by PAMPs lead to bone resorption and tissue destruction.
- PDL fibroblasts, on stimulation, lead to release of proteinases which causes direct destruction of tissue^[13].

4. Lymphocytes

- When PAMPs enter blood circulation, lymphocytes are activated
- This leads to activation of Th1 or Th2 immune response by differentiation of naive T-cells
- B-lymphocytes release antibodies against bacterial antigens, once transformed to plasma cells^[13].

5. Osteoblasts

- Release MMPs and PGE-2 in response to PAMPs, which cause tissue destruction^[13].

Viruses in periodontitis

Several studies state the involvement of viruses in causing periodontitis. Herpesvirus, human cytomegalovirus and EBV cause periodontal breakdown is supported by many studies^[16]. Recently, the antiviral innate immune response has also been explored and studied. It has been found that various viral components (genomic DNA or dsRNA) produced in

infected host cells can be recognized by TLRs^[17]. In particular TLR-2 and TLR-9 have been observed to recognize herpesvirus-associated molecules and initiate immune response. A study also states that stimulation of TLR-2 by cytomegalovirus leads to cytokine production. dsRNA can be recognized by TLR-3^[18].

TLR as potential biomarker in periodontitis

As TLRs play a dual role in periodontal health and disease, they have the capability to act as diagnostic or prognostic biomarkers for periodontitis. TLR2 and TLR4 have been detected in saliva. After SRP, a marked reduction of soluble TLR2 in saliva was observed in a study. Elevated levels of TLR4 were observed in the plasma of chronic periodontitis (CP) patients in another study^[19]. This was also seen in another study where elevated levels of IL-18 and TLR4 was seen in saliva and plasma of CP individuals^[20]. Another study found elevated levels of TLR2 and TLR4 gene expression in salivary epithelial cells of CP patients. These findings indicate that TLR2/TLR4 can be used as potential biomarkers for periodontitis^[21].

TLR and link between periodontal disease and systemic diseases

CP is associated with a number of systemic diseases as already documented in various studies present in the literature. Recently a study^[22] has stated TLR as a link between rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and periodontitis, stating the two conditions are a result of dysregulated immune response and hence, share a common pathogenesis. *P.gingivalis* and *P.nigrescence* activates the differentiation of Th17 in association with TLR2. Th17 has been observed in an increased amount in RA. Hence a link can be seen between the two conditions via TLR2^[23].

Periodontitis and diabetes mellitus (DM) are responsible for the exacerbation of one due to another. According to an immunohistochemistry study, in the sulcular epithelium and gingival CT, increased TLR2 and TLR4 were observed in patients with CP and DM^[24]. This finding is also supported by another study which reported higher concentration of TLR2, TLR4 and TLR9 in patients with CP and DM compared to CP alone^[25].

A study reported higher concentration of TSP-1 cell gene expression on being stimulated by LPS secreted by *P.gingivalis*. The gene expression was increased through the TLR2 mediated NF- κ B pathway, concluding that TLR2 may have an involvement in exacerbation of both RA and DM^[16].

According to literature available it has been established that periodontitis and cardiovascular diseases affect one another adversely. A study explored the connection between the 2 disorders and concluded that *P.gingivalis* stimulated TLR2, hindering the regenerative capacity of cardiovascular tissue. Another study stated that TLR-4 signaling pathway stimulated by *P.gingivalis* may have a significant role in atherosclerosis^[16].

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease. Hence chronically stimulated TLRs may enter the circulation and

exacerbate other systemic disorders as CP and certain systemic disorders share common signaling pathways. Hence these studies indicate that TLR is a definitive link between CP and systemic conditions and may affect each other interchangeably.

TLR and recent developments in therapeutics

As the dual role of TLRs has been established in CP via numerous studies, drugs that target TLR can act as effective therapeutics^[16].

- **Resveratrol** prevented progression of CP in mice and a marked reduction in levels of TLR4, IL-6, IL-8, TGF-alpha was also seen.
- **25-hydroxyvitamin D3** lead to reduction in levels of TLR4 and TNF-alpha in the mouse model thereby decreasing bone resorption compared to the control group.
- **Acanthoic acid** has antiinflammatory properties, and was effective in reducing TLR4 expression when HGFs were stimulated with LPS, leading to reduced production of IL-8 and IL-6.
- **JQ1**, an inhibitor of bromodomain and extraterminal domain has been observed to downregulate TLR2 and TLR4 in periodontitis mouse model and hence can be effective in decreasing cytokine production and suppressing bone resorption.
- **Topical trehalose** was tested on periodontitis rats and it downregulated TLR4 which inhibited RANKL pathway and suppressed osteoclast differentiation.
- **Baicalin**, a Chinese medicine, has been observed to inhibit TLR mediated pathways by suppressing production of IL-6 and IL-8 in LPS to stimulate human gingival epithelial cells.

These studies clearly indicate that certain drugs are effective in suppressing the TLR mediated pathway and inhibiting release of pro-inflammatory cytokines thereby preventing tissue destruction.

Conclusion

The innate and adaptive immune responses can hence be effectively regulated by TLRs. They are able to recognize the pathogens and activate the necessary signaling pathways, hence maintaining periodontal health. The adverse effect which they may have on periodontal tissues, due to chronic activation, is an area of concern and further research should focus on how to overcome it or formulate therapeutics and diagnostics to prevent the tissue destruction.

References

1. Newman MG, Takei HH, Klokkevold PR, Carranza FA (2006) Carranza's clinical periodontology. 10th ed, Saunders, St Louis, 259-274.
2. Taguchi T, Mitcham JL, Dower SK, Sims JE, Testa JR (1996) Chromosomal localization of TIL, a gene encoding a protein related to the Drosophila transmembrane receptor Toll, to human chromosome 4p14. Genomics 32, 486-488.
3. Takeda K, Akira S (2005) Toll-like receptors in innate immunity. Int

- Immunol 17, 1-14
4. Iwasaki A, Medzhitov R (2004) Toll-like receptor control of adaptive immune responses. Nat Immunol 5, 987-995
5. Dunne A, O'Neill LAJ (2003) The interleukin-1 receptor/Toll-like receptor superfamily: signal transduction during inflammation and host defense. Sci STKE 171, re3.
6. O'Neill LA (2008) When signaling pathways collide: positive and negative regulation of toll-like receptor signal transduction. Immunity 29, 12-20
7. Akira S, Takeda K. Toll-like receptor signalling. Nat Rev Immunol 2004; 4: 499-511.
8. Fitzgerald KA, Palsson-McDermott EM, Bowie AG, Jefferies CA, Mansell AS, Brady G, Brint E, Dunne A, Gray P, Harte MT, McMurray D, Smith DE, Sims JE, Bird TA, O'Neill LAJ. Mal (MyD88-adaptor-like) is required for Toll-like receptor-4 signal transduction. Nature 2001; 413: 78-83.
9. Akira S, Takeda K, Kaisho T. Toll-like receptors: critical proteins linking innate and acquired immunity. Nat Immunol 2001; 2: 675-680
10. Iwasaki A, Medzhitov R. Toll-like receptor control of adaptive immune responses. Nat Immunol 2004; 5: 987-995.
11. B Song et al (2016). The role of Toll-like receptors in periodontitis. J of Oral Med. 1-13
12. Mahanonda R et al. Toll-like receptors and their role in periodontal health and disease. Periodontology 2000, Vol. 43, 2007, 41-55
13. Hans M et al. Toll-like receptors and their dual role in peri-odontitis: a review. Journal of Oral Science, Vol. 53, No. 3, 263-271, 2011
14. Banchereau J, Steinman RM. Dendritic cells and the control of immunity. Nature 1998; 392: 245-252.
15. Krutzik SR, Tan B, Li H, Ochoa MT, Liu PT, Sharfstein SE, Graeber TG, Sieling PA, Liu YJ, Rea TH, Bloom BR, Modlin RL. TLR activation triggers the rapid differentiation of monocytes into macrophages and dendritic cells. Nat Med 2005; 11: 653-660.
16. Amit R, Morag A, Ravid Z, Hochman N, Ehrlich J, Zakay-Rones Z. Detection of herpes simplex virus in gingival tissue. J Periodontol 1992; 63: 502-506.
17. Hemmi H, Kaisho T, Takeuchi O, Sato S, Sanjo H, Hoshino K, Horiuchi T, Tomizawa H, Takeda K, Akira S. Small antiviral compounds activate immune cells via the TLR7 MyD88-dependent signaling pathway. Nat Immunol 2002; 3: 196-200.
18. Compton T, Kurt-Jones EA, Boehme KW, Belko J, Latz E, Golenbock DT, Finberg RW. Human cytomegalovirus activates inflammatory cytokine responses via CD14 and Toll-like receptor 2. J Virol 2003; 77: 4588-4596.
19. Buduneli N, Ozcaka O, Nalbantsoy A (2011). Salivary and plasma levels of toll-like receptor 2 and toll-like receptor 4 in chronic periodontitis. J Periodont 82: 878-884.
20. Banu S, Jabir NR, Mohan R et al (2015). Correlation of Tolllike receptor 4, interleukin-18, transaminases, and uric acid in patients with chronic periodontitis and healthy adults. J Periodont 86: 431-439.
21. Swaminathan V, Prakasam S, Puri V, Srinivasan M (2013). Role of salivary epithelial toll-like receptors 2 and 4 in modulating innate immune responses in chronic periodontitis. J Periodont Res 48: 757-765.
22. Lundy SK, Sarkar S, Tesmer LA, Fox DA (2007). Cells of the synovium in rheumatoid arthritis - T lymphocytes. Arthritis Res Ther 9: 202.
23. Kotake S, Yago T, Kawamoto M, Nanke Y (2012). Role of osteoclasts and interleukin-17 in the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis: crucial 'human osteoclastology'. J Bone Miner Metab 30: 125-135.
24. Promsudthi A, Poomsawat S, Limsricharoen W (2014). The role of Toll-like receptor 2 and 4 in gingival tissues of chronic periodontitis subjects with type 2 diabetes. J Periodont Res 49: 346-354.
25. Rojo-Botello NR, Garcia-Hernandez AL, Moreno-Fierros L (2012). Expression of toll-like receptors 2, 4 and 9 is increased in gingival tissue from patients with type 2 diabetes and chronic periodontitis. J Periodont Res 47: 62-73.